

PREPAREDNESS OF HOSPITALS FOR MEDICAL PROVISION TO VICTIMS OF RADIOLOGICAL TERRORISM

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the competence, training and preparedness of hospital personnel in Sofia, to provide medical care to victims of radiological terrorism and radiological accidents.

Design: We performed a cross-sectional survey using three questionnaires. Setting: 10 hospitals for active treatment in Sofia.

Participants: 19 managers, 131 doctors, 152 nurses and laboratory technicians for a total of 302 respondents.

Interventions: None.

Main Outcome Measure: We found good theoretical knowledge among physicians on the necessary medical provision in the first hours after a radiological accident, but we deem it insufficient for an adequate reaction to a large number of casualties in psychological shock, after nuclear contamination.

Results: We found that hospital personnel would not ignore patients and leave them without care in the face of realization that specific competence is lacking.

Conclusions: We found considerable deficits in, or lack thereof theoretical and practical training in dealing with victims of radiological terrorism both among nurses and laboratory technicians, and physicians, which underlines the need for offering such training.

Keywords: radiological terrorism, hospitals, preparedness.

Introduction

In the event of radiological terrorism act the health system and in particular emergency care and hospitals, should be prepared for the sudden load – providing treatment to victims, despite possible constraints: inadequate resources for the large number of casualties, lack of inexperience among medical personnel, probable fear of servicing such patients, hospitals overloaded with unscathed but frightened patients, fearing radiation and radio-nuclide contamination [1,2,3].

Studies in a number of countries – Canada [4], USA [5], Australia [6] and others provide us with a uniform picture – preparedness globally is quite low. Data from studies and experience from radiological accidents show that providing medical care to victims of radiological accident or nuclear terrorist act has its marked specifics, thus even highly qualified professionals unacquainted to the provision of medical care under time deficit and with limited diagnostic and treatment options, turn incapable of providing adequate care to victims. The process of achieving preparedness requires dedicated training, drills and organized approach to emergency care [7,8].

Materials and methods:

We performed a cross-sectional survey to gather data on the competence, training and preparedness of hospital personnel in Sofia, the capital city of Bulgaria, to provide medical care to victims of radiological terrorism and radiological accidents. Subjects studied were the management and personnel (physicians, nurses and laboratory technicians) of 10 hospitals for

active treatment in Sofia. The study involved 19 managers, 131 doctors, 152 nurses and laboratory technicians for a total of 302 respondents.

Instruments used

We developed three questionnaires targeted at three groups: hospital management, doctors, and nurses and laboratory technicians; based on literature review and recommendations of international bodies, but adapted to realities in Bulgaria.

Statistical methods used when processing data: descriptive statistics, Chi-square test, Fisher's exact test, Cramer's V contingency coefficient to test the strength of association between category data. We used SPSS version 16.0 to process data from the study.

Analysis of results and discussion:**Analysis of responses from managers**

The survey performed among managers of 10 hospitals for active treatment in Sofia presented a clear picture:

Almost all of the surveyed 19 managers believe that the risk of a radiation accident of any type on the territory of Sofia is real. Roughly half of them (47,4%) estimate this risk as minimal, 21,1% as small, and 31,5% as moderate. None of the respondents considers the risk high. Obtained answers were anticipated in light of the fact Bulgaria is not a prime target for terrorism, so the risk of radiological terrorism on the territory of Sofia is small, but should not be neglected. Bulgaria experienced a (conventional) bombing attack with 42 casualties in 2012, targeting Israeli tourists.

More than half (57.9%) of all managers admit that their hospitals lack an algorithm for action in the event

of multiple victims' scenario – e.g., multiple traumas and burns after biological, chemical or radiological accidents, terrorism or weapons application. In the event of a terrorist act with or without the release of radionuclides and with multiple casualties with combined trauma, most of the studied hospitals will face insurmountable organizational difficulties in medical provision. Hospitals will get overloaded both because of the influx of patients and deficiencies in emergency care, due to the lack of pre-planning [9,10].

More than two thirds (73,7%) of managers report, that they are planning training programs for the medical personnel on reaction in disaster situations, and 26,3% have no such plans.

It is especially important for each hospital for active treatment to have both a plan and personnel re-

serves to provide care to the priority contingents in disasters – children and pregnant women [11,12]. More than half (57.9%) of managers report having such preparation in place.

Leading researchers consider adverse psychological effects in victims of radiological terrorism, their families and society as a whole, highly likely [13,14,15]. Once it becomes known that terrorists have used a radiological dispersing device, treatment of psychological and behavioral changes in people will become as important as treatment related to direct impairment from radiation [16,17]. When asked about their plans to provide psychological support to victims of radiological accidents or terrorism, most managers (84.2%) admit they have no such plans in place (Table 1).

Table 1.

Distribution of answers on the planned psychological help provision in disasters, including radiation accidents

Is psychological help provision foreseen in disasters, including radiation accidents?	N	%
Yes	3	15,8
No	16	84,2
Total	19	100,0

Analysis of responses from medical personnel – doctors, nurses and laboratory technicians

A question of central importance to our study asked to our respondents from the medical personnel was: “What are the possible health outcomes after a radiological terrorist act?”

We find the answers we obtained alarming, to say the least.

65,6% of all surveyed physicians report that they have at least some theoretical grasp of the consequences of radiation exposure; half of them point to the early effects of radiation exposure (skin burns, acute radiation syndrome) and trauma from the blast, while the other half accentuates on late effects on cell DNA and cancer after a period of latency; but the remaining 34,4% have no idea of the effects on health. More than half (around 60%) of the nurses and laboratory technicians report being unfamiliar with the health effects of radiation exposure. The remaining 40% point out trauma and cancer.

In one of the most probable scenarios of radiological terrorism – activating a “dirty bomb” in the center of a major city – two health effects will prevail – one from the immediate blast, and one from the long-term contamination which will manifest itself after a latent period [18,19]. Consequently, the immediate needs of victims during the first hours of such a scenario, would be related to the effects of the explosion, including the psychological shock among persons not directly affected [20,21]. Affected persons with no serious trauma and emergency care indications should get completely decontaminated first, by undressing and washing the whole body [22,23,24]. Radioactive contamination should be measured, before attempting any further medical examination or treatment. Decision making is complicated in the case of severely wounded patients [25], as the urgency of surgical treatment should be judged

against the transfer of radioactive contamination in ambulances, offices and operating rooms. The problem is formulated in the statement of a senior physician working in emergency care in Vienna and experienced with radiation: “The optimal balance of medical diagnostic and therapeutic measures and requirements for radiation protection is always the most desirable” [26]. With the significance of this issue in mind, we tasked the doctors participating in the survey with ordering by importance the actions they would undertake in the first hours of a radiological accident, using numbers from 1 to 9, where 1 would designate the first and most important action and 9 the least urgent [27].

Summarizing results, this is what respondents would undertake in the first hours of the incident according to prevailing answers: 1-resuscitation, stabilizing and maintaining vital functions; 2-undressing and washing the whole body; 3-pain management; 4-trauma treatment; 5-burns treatment; 6-subsequent skin lesions treatment; 7-addressing the symptoms of radiation sickness; 8-addressing psychological effects (fear and panic); 9-accelerating the elimination of radionuclides from the body. These results demonstrate the good level of knowledge among Bulgarian physicians.

Another important question we asked was: “How would you estimate the risk to your own health when working with radioactively contaminated patients?” In order to provide a justified answer, the respondents had to first answer the following related questions:

- Do you have at your disposal in the hospital personal protective equipment for working with radioactively contaminated patients?

Almost half (48,1%) of the respondents report having personal protective equipment /listing a protective mask, gloves, lead aprons/, with which to protect exposed bodily surfaces and prevent inhaling radionuclides when taking care of a contaminated patient, and the rest (51,9%) – do not have such equipment at their

disposal or have no knowledge of the hospital having such protective equipment.

With medical nurses and laboratory technicians the situation is worse - 65% are not aware of the necessary protective equipment, the rest 35% declare that they would use protective masks, gloves, glasses, lead aprons, and lead collars, if available. Similar answers, demonstrating low levels of awareness among medical personnel have been obtained in other countries as well.

- Have you ever performed some sort of training on servicing a contaminated patient?

Answers make it clear that a small share (about one third) of all doctors, nurses and laboratory technicians have participated in such training and this happened once, so the probability of what has been learned to be long forgotten is quite real. In a study among American and Japanese medical personnel published in 2017 [28], similar results have been obtained related to the actually performed training modules on radiation exposure – over half (56%) respondents report they have received no training whatsoever, approximately one quarter have participated in one training session, 14,4% - have passed two to four courses, and 3,3% - have attended five or more.

This leads us to the conclusion medical personnel needs periodic training in sessions, where hypothetical scenarios are discussed and rehearsed. The study among American and Japanese medical personnel shows that issues with inadequate preparation persist not only in Bulgaria, but globally.

- Do physicians have at their disposal instructions for action in case of a radiological accident?

43,5% of physicians report they have such an instruction, and 56,5% – that they either don't or are not aware of its existence. Concerning this, we think a pocket guide for medical personnel would be a good option. Such guide is available online on the CDC site [29].

Having answered the three preceding questions, respondents were asked to rate their personal risk level when working with contaminated patients.

Practically all (90,8%) of the doctors recognize their personal risk when servicing a contaminated patient, and only 12 (9.2%) believe there is no risk involved. When taking into account whether physicians have attended a training course or not, it turns out that training does not change their perception of personal risk.

Similar to physicians almost all (92.8%) of the medical nurses and laboratory technicians are aware of the risks involved in servicing contaminated patients.

When comparing between responses provided by physicians and nurses (Table 2), it becomes apparent that most doctors (37.4%) rank the risk of servicing contaminated patients as small and in second place (31.3%) – as minimal, whereas most nurses (36.8%) point to a moderate risk followed by small. Only 8.4% of physicians believe the risk to be high, compared to 14.5% of nurses. The difference between the two professional groups is significant. Still, the prevailing opinions among doctors and partially among nurses, coincide with the professional consensus among radiation protection experts and it points to a relatively low risk for medical personnel but only when using proper protective gear (Table 2).

Table 2.

Rating risk when servicing a radioactively contaminated patient by doctors in comparison to nurses and laboratory technicians

Nurses and lab technicians	How would you rate risk when using necessary protective equipment?	N	%
Risk	Minimal	32	21,1
	Small	42	27,6
	Moderate	56	36,8
	High	22	14,5
	Total	152	100,0
Doctors	How would you rate risk when using necessary protective equipment?	N	%
Risk	Minimal	41	31,3
	Small	49	37,4
	Moderate	30	22,9
	High	11	8,4
	Total	131	100,0

It is important to note that it is almost impossible for a patient to be so radioactively contaminated so as to represent a real danger to providers of medical care. A possible exception is a patient with nested inside the body fragments from the initial blast.

It is logical that the perception of individual risk when servicing contaminated patients would influence the desire of medical personnel to provide care in the aftermath of a

radiological terrorist act [30]. This desire was also studied as part of our study – medics received the question: “Would you turn up in your hospital if summoned after a radiation accident with multiple casualties?”

It is encouraging to see that the majority (84.7%) of doctors in Sofia would indeed turn up, in spite of their insufficient expertise and training.

It also turns out that the expressed readiness is dependent on the availability of personal protection equipment. If they are provided a significant (80%) number of doctors would answer the call, but if they are

not provided, more than half (60%) – would not respond. Here, if we divide doctors in two groups again according to whether they received any prior training, those who have already received training would respond a lot more (95.7%) in comparison to those with no prior training (78.8%).

Responses from nurses and laboratory technicians are similar: 80.3% of them would appear for work in such emergency situations. Again, the availability of personal protection and received training increase their desire to contribute. If personal protection was available most (82.3%) would turn up, and if not, only about half of them (49.5%). Almost all (91.9%) with previous training would respond, but for those with no training the share is significantly smaller – 70%.

The real danger of radiological terrorism both globally and in our country, necessitate raising the preparedness level of hospitals to provide medical care to potential victims [31,32,33,34,35,36]. This equates a well-rehearsed individual hospitals action plans for reaction in disasters with multiple casualties, coupled with psychological support plans [37,38,39,40].

Conclusions:

- we found considerable deficits in, or lack thereof theoretical and practical training in dealing with victims of radiological terrorism both among nurses and laboratory technicians, and physicians, which underlines the need for offering such training.

- we found good theoretical knowledge among physicians on the necessary medical provision in the first hours after a radiological accident, but we deem it insufficient for an adequate reaction to a large number of casualties in psychological shock, after nuclear contamination.

- we found that hospital personnel would not ignore patients and leave them without care in the face of realization that specific competence is lacking. It is encouraging to see that the majority of respondents (80.3% of nurses and 84.7% of physicians) would respond to the call of their hospital and participate in medical provision under emergency, in spite of insufficient skills, which underscores the sense of duty of Bulgarian medical personnel.

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